

Study of the Metal Complexes of 4 (or 7)-Nitrobenzimidazoles with Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I)

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The metal complexes of 4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazole with Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I) and 2-methyl-4(or 7)-nitrobenzimidazole, 2-phenyl-4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazole with Cu(II) and Ag(I) have been synthesized. The complexes are characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, ir, electronic and esr spectra and magnetic susceptibility studies. The ligands act as bidentate ligands coordinating through the oxygen of nitro group and tertiary nitrogen of imidazole ring in all the metal ions except Ag(I), where they behave as monodentate. The esr spectra of Cu(II) complexes indicate that the complexes are covalent in nature.

BENZIMIDAZOLE containing a lone pair of electrons on tertiary nitrogen atom, acts as a ligand and forms complexes with different transition and inner transition metal ions¹⁻³. The present study was undertaken to study the effect of nitro group at 4 (or 7)-position in benzimidazole on the formation of metal complexes of transition metal ions. Synthesis and characterization of metal complexes of 4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazole (NB) with Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Ag(I), and 2-methyl-4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazole (MNB), 2-phenyl-4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazole (PNB) with Cu(II) and Ag(I) are described here.

Experimental

The ligands NB, MNB and PNB were prepared by the methods described in literature^{4,5} and recrystallized from aqueous ethanol. Their purity was checked by tlc and determining their m.p.s. Other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

The solutions of metal acetates [except Ag(I) for which silver nitrate was used] and the ligands in methanol were mixed in 1 : 2 molar proportions and refluxed on steam bath for 2-3 hr. The complex separated out on cooling to room temperature. The solid complex was filtered, washed thoroughly with

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES OF NB, MNB AND PNB WITH DIFFERENT METAL IONS

Compound	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				molar conductance mhos mole ⁻¹
		Metal	Nitrogen	Carbon	Hydrogen	
NB	Light yellow	—	—	—	—	—
[Ni(NB) ₂].Ac ₂	Yellow	11.78 (11.67)	16.62 (16.76)	42.81 (42.96)	3.12 (3.18)	43.5
[Cu(NB) ₂].Ac ₂	Green	12.42 (12.51)	16.20 (16.55)	41.81 (42.55)	3.18 (3.15)	40.5
[Zn(NB) ₂].Ac ₂	Yellow	12.62 (12.83)	16.48 (16.49)	42.55 (42.40)	3.16 (3.14)	42.0
[Cd(NB) ₂].Ac ₂	Yellow	20.18 (20.20)	15.12 (15.09)	38.65 (38.82)	2.90 (2.81)	43.2
[Hg(NB) ₂].Ac ₂	Yellow	31.22 (31.11)	13.00 (13.03)	33.62 (33.50)	2.36 (2.48)	39.5
[Ag(NB) ₂].NO ₂	Brownish red	21.60 (21.75)	20.10 (19.76)	33.83 (33.87)	2.05 (2.01)	22.6
MNB	Yellow	—	—	—	—	—
[Cu(MNB) ₂].Ac ₂	Green	11.62 (11.93)	15.52 (15.68)	44.95 (44.81)	3.59 (3.73)	41.3
[Ag(MNB) ₂].NO ₂	Brownish red	20.53 (20.59)	18.55 (18.70)	36.23 (36.65)	2.65 (2.67)	22.6
PNB	Yellow	—	—	—	—	—
[Cu(PNB) ₂].Ac ₂	Green	9.76 (9.62)	12.83 (12.73)	54.39 (54.58)	3.52 (3.63)	42.4
[Ag(PNB) ₂].NO ₂	Yellow	16.60 (16.64)	15.06 (15.12)	48.05 (48.15)	2.75 (2.77)	19.6

small quantities of methanol to remove the excess metal ions and ligand and dried over CaCl_2 in vacuum.

The metal content of a complex was estimated first by igniting the complex to its oxide and then dissolving the oxide in HNO_3 . The resulting solution was treated with known amount of EDTA solution and excess EDTA was titrated with standard zinc solution using eriochrome black T indicator. The molar conductance of the solutions of the metal complexes in nitrobenzene was measured using Systronics conductivity bridge, type-303. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord 337 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets while electronic spectra of the complexes in methanol were scanned on Shimadzu MPS-5000 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were determined using Gouy balance calibrated with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$. ESR spectra of the metal complexes were recorded on Varian V_3Q spectrophotometer. The data obtained are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The two tautomeric forms of 4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazole namely, (a) 1,7-tautomer and (b) 1,4-tautomer reacts with the metal ion to form the complex in the following manner :

Fig. 1

Tautomer (a) gives rise to a neutral compound whereas tautomer (b) gives a cationic complex. The nature of the complex formed depends on the tautomer involved in complex formation. The elemental analysis data (Table 1) reveal that all the metal ions form *bis* complexes with the ligands NB, MNB and PNB of a general formula $[\text{ML}_2]$. The molar conductance of the complexes in nitrobenzene ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution) (Table 1) indicates the involvement of 1,4-tautomer but not of 1,7-tautomer.

The broad absorption band centering at 3150 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of NB is attributed to the N-H stretching frequency⁴ and is shifted by $20\text{-}25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to lower frequencies in the metal complexes. A shift in C=N stretching frequency (1625 to 1600 cm^{-1}) and presence of N-H stretching frequency in metal complexes suggest the involvement of tertiary nitrogen of benzimidazole in coordination. Two sharp bands at 1550 and 1345 cm^{-1} , observed in the spectrum of 4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazole (characteristic of aromatic nitro group) are shifted by $10\text{-}30$

cm^{-1} in all the metal chelates except Ag(I) complexes. This suggests the participation of NO_2 group in the formation of metal chelates except that of Ag(I). The appearance of two new bands, one around $450\text{-}470 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the other around $350\text{-}390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, in the metal complexes are assigned to M—O and M—N bands. No shift in stretching frequency corresponding to acetate ion in these complexes indicates the non-participation of acetate ion in coordination. Even though the 1,7-tautomer is predominant over the 1,4-tautomer⁵, the presence of N—H band in the metal complex indicates the shift of equilibrium from 1,7- to 1,4-tautomer in presence of metal ion.

The magnetic moment values of Cu(II) complexes of NB, MNB and PNB and Ni(II) complex of NB were determined using Gouy balance at 305 K . The diamagnetic correction was applied using Pascals constants and the accuracy in the magnetic moment was in the order of ± 0.1 . The Ni(II) complex is diamagnetic whereas the Cu(II) complexes showed magnetic moments of 2.0 B.M.

The electronic spectra of Ni(II) complex of NB in methanol show three bands at 276 , 288 and 575 nm. The first two are assigned to the charge transfer bands and the third one to the transition ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_{2g}$ for square-planar nickel(II). The square-planar Cu(II) complex is expected to show two bands, one around 450 nm corresponding to ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ and the other around 600 nm corresponding to ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ transitions. The electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes of NB, PNB and MNB each show the first band at 425 , 430 and 430 nm , respectively and the second band at 580 , 540 and 540 nm , respectively. The complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) may have tetrahedral structure and the two coordinated Ag(I) complexes may have linear geometry.

The esr spectra of Cu(II) complexes showed two peaks. The values of g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} have been evaluated. The compounds $\text{Cu}(\text{NB})_2\text{Ac}_2$; $\text{Cu}(\text{MNB})_2\text{Ac}_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{PNB})_2\text{Ac}_2$ respectively show 2.082 (g_{\parallel}), 2.051 (g_{\perp}); 2.018 (g_{\parallel}), 2.004 (g_{\perp}) and 2.064 (g_{\parallel}), 2.014 (g_{\perp}). Values of g_{\parallel} are suggestive of strong covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds⁷.

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